

Study Consent Information

Title of Study: Refactoring and Review as Comparative Tasks

Sections of this document have been redacted to preserve anonymity during the review process.

1. Email *

What are some general things you should know about research studies?

You are invited to take part in a research study. Your participation in this study is voluntary. You have the right to be a part of this study, to choose not to participate, and to stop participating at any time without penalty. The purpose of this research study is to gain a better understanding of how developers compare and evaluate code alternatives. We will do this through a series of software refactoring and review tasks.

You are not guaranteed any personal benefits from being in this study. Research studies also may pose risks to those who participate. You may want to participate in this research because its relationship to your class and potential for extra credit. You may not want to participate in this research because your behavior during the task may be used anonymously in scientific research.

Specific details about the research in which you are invited to participate are contained below. If you do not understand something in this form, please ask the researcher for clarification or more information. A copy of this consent form will be provided to you. If, at any time, you have questions about your participation in this research, do not hesitate to contact the researcher(s) named above or the [REDACTED] IRB office. The IRB office's contact information is listed in the "What if you have questions about your rights as a research participant?" section of this form.

What is the purpose of this study?

The purpose of this study is to learn more about how developers investigate multiple code snippets at a time in order to answer questions about their relationship and similarity. This research will help the design of future tools for code search and comprehension.

How many people will be in the study?

This study is open to students of [REDACTED], and will therefore have up to 130 participants.

Am I eligible to be a participant in this study?

If you are a registered student in [REDACTED], you are eligible to participate in this study. You cannot otherwise.

What will happen if you take part in the study?

[REDACTED]

Additionally, if you volunteer, you will be eligible to participate in an extra-credit interview following before the study. This interview, which will happen over Zoom, will discuss your experience and perspectives on code review and refactorings. The audio to this interview will be recorded. The extra credit will be distributed as described in the course syllabus. Other extra credit opportunities that do not involve participating in research studies are also described in the syllabus.

If you do not volunteer your data for research, you are not eligible for the interview and extra credit.

The total amount of time that you will be participating in this study is 75 minutes. If you also participate in the interview, the total time will be 90 minutes (75 minutes in class, 15 minutes outside class).

What if you have questions about this study?

If you have questions about the study, you can either contact the instructor or researcher (see emails at the top of this form) or ask during class time.

What if you have questions about your rights as a research participant?

If you have questions about your rights or are concerned with your treatment throughout the research process, please contact [REDACTED]

2. I consent to the use of my data for research.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Interview Consent

3. Do you volunteer for an optional interview about refactoring and review over Zoom for extra credit?

We anticipate this takes about 15 minutes.

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

Interview Scheduling

Please schedule an interview on this calendar: [REDACTED]

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

